

THE STRUCTURE AND GEOCHEMISTRY OF THE KILA-KUPRA MUD VOLCANO (GEORGIA)

Glonti, (Bacho) V.¹, Koiava, K.², Kotulová, J.³, and Kvaliashvili, L.⁴

¹ Frontera Resources, 12 Paliashvili St., Tbilisi, Georgia 0179

bglonti@fronteraresources.com

² Al. Janelidze Institute of Geology of Iv. Javakishvili Tbilisi State University, 5 Politkovskaya str., Tbilisi, Georgia 0186

koiava_ka@yahoo.com

³ Energy & Geoscience Laboratory, Joint Laboratory of Energy & Geoscience Institute at University of Utah and Geological Institute of Slovak Academy of Sciences

9 Dubravska cesta, P.O. Box 106

SK 840 05 Bratislava, Slovak Republic

jkotuliva@egi.utah.edu

⁴ LTD "GeoEngService", 166 Ambrolauri St. block 5, Tbilisi, Georgia 0160

lkvaliashvili@yahoo.com

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Introduction

Georgia is the one of the countries where mud volcanoes are widespread. Within Georgia, their core distribution area encompasses the Iori plateau and the Gombori range (Kakheti region). Minor occurrences are observed in the northern flank foothills of the Trialeti range near the village of Kavtiskhevi (Ebralidze et al., 1975).

Methodology

The Kila-Kupra fold is complicated by exposures of three mud volcanoes (Kila-Kupra East, Central, and West, Fig. 1) and is located in the central part of the Iori plateau. Investigation of the genesis of the above-mentioned mud volcanoes included water and oil sampling of the gryphon for geochemistry studies. The samples were shipped to the Energy and Geoscience Institute at the University of Utah and are currently being processing. Aside from geochemical studies provided by the "Frontera Eastern Georgia" company designed to gain a better understanding of the structure of the Kila-Kupra mud volcanoes, 2D seismic data have been analyzed using IHS Kingdom software (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. A: Geological map of the Kila-Kupra area with the location of mud volcanoes and seismic lines; B: Interpretation of Seismic line A-A¹; C: Interpretation of Seismic line B-B¹.

Results

As a result of the seismic data processing (Fig. 1), it is now known that the Kila-Kupra mud volcanoes are related to the asymmetric anticline structure that is complicated by the fault dome of the same name. Apparently, the Middle Sarmatian sediments are the source of these volcanoes. To date, based on paleontological and petrographic studies of mud volcano breccia samples, Upper Sarmatian sediments have been regarded as the source of the Kila-Kupra volcanoes (Ebralidze et al., 1975; Buleishvili, 1960). However, the presence of *Porosonion subgranosum* (Egger) and *Nonion bogdanowiczi* Voloshinova in the foraminifera complexes introduced in the cited publications indicates the existence of older than Upper Sarmatian sediment material (apparently Middle Sarmatian) in the mud volcano breccias as well (Gruzinskaya et al., 1986; Koiava et al., 2008).

Conclusions

On the basis of the studies conducted and available data, that Kila-Kupra mud volcanoes are related to the asymmetric anticline structure complicated by the fault dome of the same name. A possible link between the source of these mud volcanoes and Middle Sarmatian sediments has been proposed.

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